

FDO Bulletin 2024-2

October 2024

FDO Conference 2025 in Washington DC

FDOF Phase II

FDO Conference 2025 in Washington DC - preparation started, comments welcome
FDO Forum Phase II - FDOF Phase I finished, become active
GIDS Architecture Work - Workshop on Layered Architecture with IDSA Technology
FDO One project finalized - various outputs amongst which a full FDO Implementation
FDO Specs, Implementation Variants, Compliance Profiles - next step, participate
Platform for Applications - to disseminate your solutions, participate
FDO Operations & Active FDOs - 3 papers are now in preparation, a White Paper is ready
Announcements (NFDI4DataScience Hackathon, CODATA CDIF, African FDO Info day)

FDO Conference 2025 in Washington DC

In the autumn of 2025 we will organize the next FDO conference in Washington DC. This conference will foster a few topics of high relevance: (1) the layered architecture of the global integrated dataspace with FDOs as basic layer, (2) Interoperability challenges at the basic layers, (3) FDO implementations and applications, (4) advancing the International FDO Testbed, (5) new opportunities given by FDO Operations and Active FDOs.

A recent workshop has shown that also industry is very much interested to come to a well-structured architecture allowing to identify layers (see below). We already have good involvement from industry, including Microsoft, who has tentatively offered use of a venue in Arlington, Virginia. The FDO Forum will, of course, need to maintain its independence, but uptake of the FDO concept by industry is of interest. A call for papers will be disseminated soon.

Comments and suggestions to the conference topics are welcome.

FDO Forum Phase II

The FDO Forum took the time to deeply discuss the changed situation and the challenges to be tackled in Phase II. Phase I (January 2020 to June 2024) was devoted to understanding what an FDO is, where it fits into the landscape of data standards being suggested, and to develop first implementations and applications which are using FDOs. The achievements of Phase I: (1) The concept of FDOs is widely known and resonates now even in industry. (2) The basic specifications have been developed leaving space for different implementations. (3) A few implementations have been developed claiming compliance with the specs. (4) An increasing number of applications have been developed often in isolated projects. Therefore, Phase I was successful, knowing that the transition we are aiming at with FDOs will take a long time and require patience and persistence.

For Phase II the FDO Forum needs to manage an organizational refreshment, redefine its goals, maintain FDOF as an independent initiative and organize annual meetings. The organizational structure needs a simplification and an adjustment of the committees to meet the changed requirements. The focus of the work in Phase II will be on (1) consolidating and polishing the specifications and their refinement where necessary, (2) intensify the work on compliance checks and interoperability, (3) inform about the many applications and bring the active people together, (4) work on the layered architecture of the global integrated dataspace and collaborate with industry and standard organizations in this endeavor, and (5) work on new challenges such as FDO Operations and Active FDOs.

These new directions for FDOF will now be turned into actions by the Co-Chairs, the Steering Committee and the Technical Specification and Implementation Group (TSIG). Anyone interested in participating on this path and bringing in his/her ideas is welcome.

FDOF will now start adjusting its organizational structure and turning the intended goals into actions.

GIDS Architecture

The recent FDO Architecture workshop (documents see below) showed that the concept of FDOs is fairly much overlapping with what was discussed for example by the IDSA (International Dataspace Association) Architecture Working Group led by Microsoft, for example. The basic FDO mechanisms do not deal with interpreting rights, but must be able to securely transport access specifications to a next layer extending

FDOs by using FDO Operation mechanisms or applying a data usage control layer as designed by the Eclipse Dataspace Components. The principles are indicated in the diagram which is widely accepted now.

Deeper discussions are required to (1) understand how FDO would fit with the new IDSA architecture design, (2) how FDO Operations and Active FDOs can be used to control data usage, and (3) how all these mechanisms can best be used to guarantee data sovereignty and thus increase trust which finally will be the core criterion to increase data sharing in science, public services and especially industry. Therefore, we see the coming FDO 2025 conference as a milestone to bring experts from different sectors together and have a deep discussion.

Material about the recent workshop and the different presentations can be found here:

(<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1qLNxu-5NWapVzJwzIqfjISofB50mDkGu?usp=sharing>)

A White Paper on Active FDOs can be found here: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1YtQRTnvaK-LQaVaNjWMHZg3ohZzcJGHZ/view?usp=sharing>

FDO TSIG already has a subgroup working on FDO Operations and Active FDOs and will extend its activities on this topic to include architectural aspects. Experts who are interested in these topics should send a note to nicolas.blumenroehr@kit.edu or peter.wittenburg@mpi.nl.

FDO One Project

The FDO One project finished its work and met its original aims after roughly 8 months of goal driven work which was completely aligned with the FDO specifications: (1) It created an initial local FDO Tested by adapting and integrating 5 different repository systems (Dataverse, B2Share, LinkAhead, S3 Object Cloud Store and Cordra) and developing an FDO Manager supporting a few workflows to manage FDOs in this heterogeneous space. (2) It worked out a set of MoUs with partners in different continents to extend this initial Testbed to an international one and is organizing information days and training sessions. (3) It created bridges to industry standards such as IDSA EDC and Industry 4.0 AAS so that such services can be integrated into the FDO domain and implemented a use case allowing users to make use of the information in such dataspace. (4) It worked on an architecture for GIDS, made a suggestion of how to move on in the interaction with standardization organizations and contributed to the work on FDO Operations and Active FDOs.

Some decisions needed to be taken to come to full-fledged FDO Implementation that are beyond the FDO specifications and these need now to be documented and communicated with the FDO Forum. The material including the code can be found via the FDO One web-site: <https://fdo-one.org/>

The FDO One project will continue its work beyond the project end in close collaboration with the FDO Forum and will organize information days and training courses. Questions can be directed to sven.bingert@gwdg.de.

FDO Specifications, Implementation Variants and Compliance Profiles

It is important to again mention the simple basic FDO Specifications which should be met by all implementations that use the term "FDO". As George Strawn likes to point out, **basic data FDOs are nothing else than machine actionable bundles of data and all kinds of metadata identified by a PID.** This minimal specification leads to a few formalisms:

- ***A PIDs resolves to an FDO record.***
- ***The FDO Record contains a set of kernel attributes and is defined by an FDO profile.***
- ***The FDO Profile follows simple specifications.***
- ***All kernel attributes being used in a profile need to be defined and registered.***
- ***There are only two mandatory kernel attributes: reference to the FDO Profile and the FDO Type. For Data FDOs there must be references to the bit sequence and to metadata.***

Of course, communities can extend the set of kernel attributes to whatever they like to include as long as these attributes are well-defined and registered. Such basic FDOs can be linked with operations and even be extended to Active FDOs which are autonomously acting agents.

At the Berlin summit we have seen 28 presentations about concrete FDO implementation variants and applications and this number will increase in the coming years. Major implementation variants can be identified such as RO-Crate, Nano-Pubs and FDO One which are being used in a variety of applications. In the coming phase we need to study the differences between all those variants to improve interoperability. The FAIR principles are recommendations which resulted in a huge amount of interpretations and actions. The FAIR DOs are specifications for a basic exchange mechanism where a high level of coherence will be needed to achieve basic interoperability. TSIG already finished one first overview about the various solutions that are related with FDOs to describe the landscape. The document can be found here:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1tAybnGsL3_1a135ILRgYyJntUTNPHqtO6N9dnB_TbAQ/edit?usp=sharing

A second document comparing solutions in great detail is still in progress.

Therefore, the FDO2025 conference will have “Interoperability” as one of its focus themes. A good preparation for this discussion is to kick off the work on FDO Compliance Profiles as suggested by Erik Schultes. These FDO CP should be filled in by all developers working on implementations and applications in the coming months. An online tool will be worked out in collaboration with GO FAIR.

We will contact implementation and application developers to help us in preparing the interoperability session in FDO 2025 and the FDO CP will be made available for everyone interested.

Platform for Applications & Dissemination

The FDO Forum focused in Phase 1 on infrastructure aspects and this work needs to be continued. But it was realized that in Phase 2 we should spend much more effort on applications and offer a platform for all developers that use FDOs and DOA¹ to solve practical problems in science and business. We will set up a group that will focus on applications and will look for a collaboration with RDA. In addition, we would like to invite experts to participate in this group to spread information about the spectrum of applications, the motivations to use FDOs and the state of work.

Anyone who is working on an FDO application, which was not presented or included at the Berlin meeting, and/or would like to join the new group is welcome to send a note to sven.bingert@gwdg.de

FDO Operations & Active FDOs

The TSIG Subgroup working on FDO Operations and Active FDOs is working on 3 papers describing the linking to operations and the details of Active FDOs. A White Paper describing Active FDOs can be found here:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1YtQRTnvaK-LQaVaNiWMHZg3ohZzcJGHZ/view?usp=sharing>

Questions and comments can be sent to nicolas.blumenroehr@kit.edu.

¹ DOA stands for Digital Object Architecture. It is quite close to FDOs, however lacks a few specs. It is used in some areas of industry and therefore needs to be included to get a comprehensive overview.

Announcements

Hackathon. The ZB MED institute from Köln/DE, in collaboration with Claus Weiland from the Senckenberg Society for Nature Research and Stian Soiland-Reyes from The University of Manchester, will run an **NFDI4DataScience Hackathon in Cologne, Germany on 20-22.Nov.2024** (from noon to noon) on "webby" FDOs using RO-Crate and FAIR Signposting. A limited number of scholarships to partially cover the participation will be sponsored by NFDI4DataScience. More information and application details can be found at

<https://zbmed.github.io/nfdi4ds-hackathons/docs/2024.html#webby-fdos-with-ro-crates-and-fair-signposting>.

Joint FDO/CDIF Workshop (26.11.2024 15.00 CET). The recently launched [Cross Domain Interoperability Framework \(CDIF\)](#) was developed through the [WorldFAIR project](#), coordinated by [CODATA](#), and is based on a set of concrete, implementation-level principles intended to enhance any community's data management approaches and reduce the barriers to reusing data across domains. CDIF provides recommended standards and approaches to building different levels of interoperability needed for cross-domain data reuse, supported by implementation guidance. Taking a modular approach, the first CDIF report identifies five functional requirements and provides recommendations and implementation guidance for these. Work on further CDIF profiles and implementation projects are underway. They are coordinated by CODATA as [WorldFAIR+](#), and will contribute to the process of refining and extending CDIF.

Agenda: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1k8AFrnGVKCA5j48GqCMirGDEblyEfbJl/view?usp=sharing>

Registration: <https://us02web.zoom.us/meeting/register/tZAsc-2sqDkuEtHV1oQPbFLGL7sS8ci0UzBd#/registration>

FDOs in Africa. The FDO One project, FDOF, African OS Platform, NICIS and GWDG organized an FDO Info Day with 144 registrants from 22 different African countries to spread the knowledge about FDOs, to foster the building of stable repositories and to integrate repositories into the emerging International FDO Testbed. These information days will be repeated. Questions and comments can be sent to Peter.wittenburg@mpi.nl. Information can be found here:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Q-5cNb2viNVUVitDYFZTd8Zloszitawu/edit?usp=sharing&ouid=102759110256334692620&rtpof=true&sd=true>

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